

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Mapping Virtual Millitomes to Reference Organs

Using 3D millitome mesh-based models to scale tissue registration into the Human Reference Atlas

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Introduction

The millitome defines a guide for scaling up tissue registration by partitioning a human organ model and computationally registering the resulting tissue blocks into extraction sites within the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) three-dimensional (3D) reference system. The guide can be implemented using (1) detailed instructions for surgeons on how to extract tissues from a human body or (2) a 3D cutting mold to be used when entire organs are cut into extraction sites. In both cases, AutoMated Alignment and Projection (AMAP) toolkit documented in this [GitHub repository](#) (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science, Indiana University 2023) is used to align cutting instructions or 3D molds to the HRA reference organs. Using a lookup table that assigns tissue specimen IDs to cut tissue blocks, data can be added and explored in the Exploration User Interface (EUI). This workflow reduces the time and increases the efficiency of registering tissue into the HRA.

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) outlines the steps for aligning a virtual millitome to a 3D reference object in the HRA to register the sectioned blocks into extraction sites within the HRA 3D reference system. It generates the required files for ingestion into the HRA Knowledge Graph (HRA-KG) and publishes them in the EUI. The virtual millitome includes a 3D model (STL/GLB file) along with a sectioning protocol and a block assignment table used by the data provider. **Fig. 1** provides a schematic overview of this process.

The primary audiences for this SOP are teams who want to scale up registrations using their own millitomes. This SOP assumes basic familiarity with Python and 3D modeling. Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**.

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Figure 1. Overview of the Automated Alignment and Projection (AMAP) process

To learn more about the creation of 3D reference organs in the HRA, please read the accompanying SOPs titled [Creating 3D Models from Datasets](#) (Schlehlein and Quardokus 2022) and [3D Reference Object Approval](#) (Quardokus et al. 2022). To learn more about creating and using a millitome, please read the accompanying SOPs titled [Constructing a Millitome and Generating Virtual Tissue Blocks](#) (Kienle et al. 2023) and [Using a Millitome](#) (Bueckle and Kienle 2022).

Roles and Responsibilities

The **AMAP Developer** is responsible for writing code to generate projections and produce the specific data files needed for integrating millitomes into the EUI and the HRA knowledge graph (HRA-KG).

The **Data Provider** is responsible for providing a 3D model of the millitome as an STL or GLB file, the sectioning protocol that was used to cut the sample into blocks and assign labels, a lookup table for mapping label assignments to millitome blocks, and metadata about the tissue samples and their respective donor.

The **RUI Coordinator** is responsible for creating a millitome registration set using the millitome projections, lookup information, and metadata.

The **HRA Technical Lead** is responsible for reviewing the generated data files, ingesting them into the HRA knowledge graph, and publishing digital objects.

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Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
AMAP Developer	Yashvardhan Jain	yashjain@iu.edu
Data Provider	various	various
RUI Coordinator	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu
Technical Director	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu

Procedures

Obtain individual blocks from the 3D composite millitome model

A millitome model file describes a valid 3D model created following the procedure outlined in the SOP titled Constructing a Millitome and Generating Virtual Tissue Blocks (Kienle et al. 2023). It comes in various file formats, e.g., VTK or STL. The first consideration is whether the file represents virtual tissue blocks as individual geometries or as composite geometry, i.e., a single 3D model. While only the composite geometry is needed to generate the projections, access to individual blocks is required to define individual tissue block extraction sites for integration into the EUI and HRA-KG, warranting a necessary conversion step that does the following:

- Run `vtk_to_millitome.py` (see **Table 2** for specifications).
- Read the obtained millitome 3D file with point data (vertex) labels. Each vertex must be labeled in the composite geometry in order for the process to separate out the individual blocks. The number of unique labels may or may not match the number of expected blocks in the millitome according to the label specification file. Extra labels will be removed in a later step.
- Generate a new 3D file in the GLB format with the blocks (as implied by their vertex labels) as individually accessible geometries in a scene.
- Export the file to any accessible path on the system.

Table 2. Data read and generated by the VTK to millitome conversion code.

Input	Output	Tool
3D model file (usually a VTK or STL file) Note: Each vertex should have at least integer labels indicating the millitome block the vertex is a part of	3D model scene file in the GLB format with individual millitome blocks separated as individual geometries	Python Code

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Labeling the millitome blocks according to specification

The Data Provider must supply a sectioning protocol that assigns a unique label to each millitome block. An excerpt of a [sectioning protocol](#) for the ovary by Stephen Fisher (Department of Biology, University of Pennsylvania) is shown in **Fig. 2**.

Figure 2. Label assignments for the ovary millitome.

In the future, these labels will be included as part of the 3D model file, but as of version 1.0.0 of these procedures, the mapped millitomes (pancreas, ovary, uterus) have not had matching labels on the model itself. That is, the labels on the model do not necessarily match the labels in the specification file. This relabeling is done manually using the open source digital content creation 3D software program Blender (see **Table 3** for specifications). The steps are as follows:

- Read the processed GLB file in Blender (or any other digital content creation software). All the blocks should show up as individual member meshes grouped under a global parent.
- Click on each block from the equivalent scene explorer window and rename it according to the label specification file.
- Export the file as a GLB file with the blocks relabeled.

Table 3. Data read and generated by the manual labeling procedure using Blender.

Input	Output	Tool
3D model scene file in the GLB format	3D model scene file in the GLB format with blocks relabeled	Blender 4.2 (Blender Foundation, n.d.)

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	according to the specification file	
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Removal of any unlabeled geometric artifacts

There may be unnecessary vertices (geometries) that contain a vertex label in the 3D model file, but are not acknowledged in the specification file. Remove these from the GLB file unless they are explicitly required by the Data Provider. All vertices will be transformed from the first atlas reference to the second atlas reference, so unnecessary vertices should be removed to reduce crowding in the resulting projection. Unnecessary geometry should be removed whenever possible as a recommended best practice (see **Table 4** for specifications).

- Read the processed GLB file in Blender or any other digital content creation software. All the blocks should show up as individual member meshes grouped under a global parent, with labels that match the specification file.
- Select blocks in the scene explorer that do not have a corresponding label in the specification file (see **Fig. 3.**), and delete them from the scene.
- Export the file as a GLB.
- At this point, a GLB file with the correct labels and no unlabeled blocks has been produced.

Figure 3. Blender Viewport highlighting geometry that does not have a vertex label in the label specification file provided by the Data Provider.

Table 4. Data read and generated by the manual deletion procedure using the Blender tool.

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Input	Output	Tool
3D model scene file in the GLB format	3D model scene file in the GLB format with blocks relabeled and unwanted geometry (blocks) deleted.	Blender 4.2 (Blender Foundation, n.d.) Note: This is the current long term support version, but any version would work for this task

Generating files for HRA-KG ingestion using AMAP

AMAP (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science, Indiana University 2023) aligns the millitome GLB file and the HRA; for example, between the ovary millitome and the HRA right ovary shown in **Fig. 1**. The alignment refers to the sequence of matrix transformations for moving each vertex on the source atlas (the millitome) to approximate the reference atlas (the HRA right ovary), see **Fig. 1**. For an alignment between two point-clouds (derived from the mesh models), the registrations are applied sequentially; rigid registration finds the best overlap between the global shapes, which non-rigid registration then fine-tunes for the best local fit. The result is a transformation matrix which defines the linear transformation (scale, rotation, and translation) for the best global fit, and a non-linear deformation vector field which specifies how each of the points must move for the best local fit. These transformations are then applied to produce two JSON-LD files (see **Table 5** for specifications) in the specific schema required for ingestion into the Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph (HRA-KG):

- Clone or download the AMAP code repository from GitHub (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science, Indiana University 2023) and follow the instructions to set up the software.
- Download the target HRA reference organ you would like to map the millitome to, such as the right ovary from the Human Reference Atlas.
- Follow the millitome alignment tutorial [Python Code](#), replacing local paths to the respective model files.
- Obtain two .jsonld files as output (see **Fig. 4** and **Fig. 5**, for an example):
 - extraction-sites.jsonld (defines the spatial placement of mapped millitome blocks to the reference organ).
 - dataset-graph.jsonld (defines the virtual donors and virtual tissue blocks in addition to the mapped placements).

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```
[
  {
    "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
    "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-male#25",
    "@type": "SpatialEntity",
    "label": "25",
    "creator": "Bhargav Snehal Desai",
    "creator_first_name": "Bhargav Snehal",
    "creator_last_name": "Desai",
    "creator_orcid": "https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6509-7698",
    "creation_date": "2024-08-15",
    "x_dimension": 20.762410956377238,
    "y_dimension": 22.002622559289254,
    "z_dimension": 26.837080782615306,
    "dimension_units": "millimeter",
    "placement": {
      "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
      "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-male#25_placement",
      "@type": "SpatialPlacement",
      "placement_date": "2024-08-15",
      "x_scaling": 1,
      "y_scaling": 1,
      "z_scaling": 1,
      "scaling_units": "ratio",
      "x_rotation": 0,
      "y_rotation": 0,
      "z_rotation": 0,
      "rotation_order": "XYZ",
      "rotation_units": "degree",
      "x_translation": 100.23296812999057,
      "y_translation": 60.58372915583213,
      "z_translation": 13.462135774533369,
      "translation_units": "millimeter",
      "target": "http://purl.org/ccf/latest/ccf.owl#VHMPancreas"
    },
    "ccf_annotations": [
      "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001151"
    ]
  },
  {
    "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
    "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-male#C24",
    "@type": "SpatialEntity",
    "label": "C24",
```

Figure 4. Partial view of extraction-sites.jsonld file generated by AMAP, containing metadata compatible with the Exploration User Interface and the HRA-KG.

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```
{
  "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl#Donor1",
      "@type": "Donor",
      "label": "Male",
      "description": "Entered 7/14/2024, Bhargav Snehal Desai, MC-IU",
      "link": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl",
      "consortium_name": "HRA",
      "provider_name": "MC-IU",
      "provider_uuid": "87751d4c-a850-4e2c-84dc-da6a797d76de",
      "sex": "Male",
      "samples": [
        {
          "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl#Donor1_TissueBlock1",
          "@type": "Sample",
          "sample_type": "Tissue Block",
          "label": "Registered 7/14/2024, Bhargav Snehal Desai, MC-IU",
          "description": "20.762410956377238 x 22.002622559289254 x 26.837080782615306 millimeter, 26.837080782615306 millimeter",
          "link": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl",
          "section_count": 0,
          "section_size": 26.837080782615306,
          "rui_location": {
            "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
            "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl#25",
            "@type": "SpatialEntity",
            "label": "25",
            "creator": "Bhargav Snehal Desai",
            "creator_first_name": "Bhargav Snehal",
            "creator_last_name": "Desai",
            "creator_orcid": "https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6509-7698",
            "creation_date": "2024-08-15",
            "x_dimension": 20.762410956377238,
            "y_dimension": 22.002622559289254,
            "z_dimension": 26.837080782615306,
            "dimension_units": "millimeter",
            "placement": {
              "@context": "https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ontology/ccf-context.jsonld",
              "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl#25_placement",
              "@type": "SpatialPlacement",
              "placement_date": "2024-08-15",
              "x_scaling": 1,
              "y_scaling": 1,
              "z_scaling": 1,
              "scaling_units": "ratio",
              "x_rotation": 0,
              "y_rotation": 0,
              "z_rotation": 0,
              "rotation_order": "XYZ",
              "rotation_units": "degree",
              "x_translation": 100.23296812999057,
              "y_translation": 60.58372915583213,
              "z_translation": 13.462135774533369,
              "translation_units": "millimeter",
              "target": "http://purl.org/ccf/latest/ccf.owl#VHMPancreas"
            },
            "ccf_annotations": [
              "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001151"
            ]
          },
          "ccf_annotations": [
            "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001151"
          ]
        },
        {
          "@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/pancreas-male-pnnl#Donor1_TissueBlock2",
          "@type": "Sample",
          "sample_type": "Tissue Block",

```

Figure 5. Partial view of dataset-graph.jsonld file generated by AMAP, containing metadata compatible with the Exploration User Interface and the HRA-KG. Each labeled block in the millitome becomes an extraction site with required and compatible metadata.

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Table 5. Data read and generated for preparing the mapped millitome (using AMAP) for HRA-KG ingestion.

Input	Output	Tool
3D model scene file in GLB format and 3D model file in GLB format downloaded from the HRA portal	Dataset-graph.jsonld and extraction-sites.jsonld	Python Code and AMAP code repository

Review and publish as an HRA digital object

The files produced in the previous step are uploaded to a staging location, <https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-amap/tree/main/output-data/millitome>, where they are handed over to the Technical Director.

- The files then go through a manual review process by the Technical Director, who ensures that all the fields such as the @id in the extraction-sites.jsonld are correct.
- The Technical Director then creates the metadata.yaml file which includes the title of the millitome being mapped and other relevant information about the creator, reviewer, etc. (see **Fig. 6** for an example).

```
1 title: Millitome for Generic Pancreas, Female
2 description: Millitome for Generic Pancreas, Female
3 creators:
4   - fullName: Bhargav Desai
5     firstName: Bhargav
6     lastName: Desai
7     orcid: 0009-0008-6509-7698
8 project_leads:
9   - fullName: Katy Börner
10     firstName: Katy
11     lastName: Börner
12     orcid: 0000-0002-3321-6137
13 reviewers:
14   - fullName: Ellen M. Quardokus
15     firstName: Ellen
16     lastName: Quardokus
17     orcid: 0000-0001-7655-4833
18 externalReviewers: []
19 creation_date: '2024-08-07'
20 license: >-
21   Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International ([CC BY
22   4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/))
23 publisher: HuBMAP
24 funders:
25   - funder: National Institutes of Health
26     awardNumber: OT20D026671
27 datatable:
28   - extraction-sites.jsonld
```

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Figure 6. Partial view of metadata.yaml file containing millitome-specific metadata for final publication in the HRA-KG.

- The files dataset-graph.jsonld and extraction-sites.jsonld, including metadata.yaml, are moved to a staging area for the HRA-KG by the Technical Director (see **Table 6** for specifications), <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/millitome>, where they are placed in their own, organ-specific folder.
- From this staging location, the extraction sites from the millitome are automatically ingested into the Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph (HRA-KG) as a published digital object that is visible and can be found at <https://lod.humanatlas.io/millitome>.
- Additionally, the data is inserted into the SPARQL database, which then makes it queryable using the HuBMAP API, found at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/api/#get-v1/extraction-site>.

Table 6. Data read and generated for the review and publication of the mapped millitome as a digital object.

Input	Output	Tool
Dataset-graph.jsonld and extraction-sites.jsonld	metadata.yaml, dataset-graph.jsonld*, and extraction-sites.jsonld* at https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-kg/tree/main/digital-objects/millitome Published digital object at https://lod.humanatlas.io/millitome	Manual process facilitated by the Technical Director

Link data using lookup table and publish the dataset graph

The lookup table is most commonly a spreadsheet that specifies the corresponding millitome block for the registered samples (see **Fig. 7** for an example). While this has been a common method, it is not necessary that the lookup information to map the registered tissue data to the millitome blocks is provided as depicted in this document. The names of the columns and format might change. In such cases, the RUI Coordinator is responsible for ensuring an appropriate way to create the <ruj_location.jsonld>

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	A	B	C	D	E
1	millitome_ID	sample_lab_id	Tissue Block HuBMAP IDs	RUI Location	Link
2	A1	PE-1A	HBM625.ZFTZ.894	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A1"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM625.ZFTZ.894
3	B1	PE-1B	HBM859.DZPK.256	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B1"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM859.DZPK.256
4	C1	PE-1C	HBM527.VMNR.723	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C1"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM527.VMNR.723
5	D1	PE-1D	HBM685.VIVH.785	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D1"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM685.VIVH.785
6	A2	CLR-2A	HBM833.JPZG.893	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A2"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM833.JPZG.893
7	B2	CLR-2B	HBM329.BFHH.463	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B2"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM329.BFHH.463
8	C2	CLR-2C	HBM958.LBIH.999	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C2"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM958.LBIH.999
9	D2	CLR-2D	HBM377.WDKH.475	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D2"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM377.WDKH.475
10	A3	PCMC-3A	HBM869.FJXG.495	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A3"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM869.FJXG.495
11	B3	PCMC-3B	HBM927.QBZP.837	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B3"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM927.QBZP.837
12	C3	PCMC-3C	HBM293.ZZWZ.357	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C3"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM293.ZZWZ.357
13	D3	PCMC-3D	HBM442.TVMK.429	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D3"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM442.TVMK.429
14	A4	FCMC-4A	HBM484.CKHP.546	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A4"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM484.CKHP.546
15	B4	FCMC-4B	HBM385.FTIL.493	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B4"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM385.FTIL.493
16	C4	FCMC-4C	HBM279.ZBFG.324	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C4"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM279.ZBFG.324
17	D4	FCMC-4D	HBM674.MWZD.688	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D4"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM674.MWZD.688
18	A5	FF-5A	HBM883.PSDQ.427	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A5"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM883.PSDQ.427
19	B5	FF-5B	HBM527.NKJ.929	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B5"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM527.NKJ.929
20	C5	FF-5C	HBM973.ZLKQ.336	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C5"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM973.ZLKQ.336
21	D5	FF-5D	HBM876.MXVS.964	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D5"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM876.MXVS.964
22	A6	RNA-6A	HBM246.CHBX.834	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A6"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM246.CHBX.834
23	B6	RNA-6B	HBM766.MZBD.225	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B6"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM766.MZBD.225
24	C6	RNA-6C	HBM757.TRPD.633	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C6"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM757.TRPD.633
25	D6	RNA-6D	HBM557.HCGR.966	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D6"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM557.HCGR.966
26	A7	PE-7A	HBM649.JXJ.663	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A7"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM649.JXJ.663
27	B7	PE-7B	HBM585.QZJW.757	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B7"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM585.QZJW.757
28	C7	PE-7C	HBM976.ZRGZ.727	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#C7"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM976.ZRGZ.727
29	D7	PE-7D	HBM546.DGDM.997	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#D7"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM546.DGDM.997
30	A8	CLR-8A	HBM553.NXDC.839	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#A8"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM553.NXDC.839
31	B8	CLR-8B	HBM729.SWHH.556	{"@id": "https://purl.humanatlas.io/millitome/generic-pancreas-female#B8"}	https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/browse/HBM729.SWHH.556

Figure 7. An example of a lookup file for the Vanderbilt Pancreas. The Tissue Block HuBMAP IDs column is used to identify registered HuBMAP data, and the millitome_ID column refers to the corresponding millitome block for the registered sample.

- The RUI Coordinator creates a millitome registration set by assembling a registrations.yaml file that contextualizes the digital object using the lookup and metadata information from the Data Provider (see **Fig. 8**).

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The figure shows two side-by-side windows. The left window displays a YAML file with registration information for the HuBMAP consortium. It includes details like provider name (Vanderbilt University), defaults (id and link), and a list of donors. For each donor, there are samples with their own labels, links, IDs, and RUI locations. The right window shows a spreadsheet titled 'VU Pancreas Lookup.xlsx' with columns for 'millitome_ID', 'sample_lab_id', and 'Tissue Block HuBMAP IDs'. The rows in the spreadsheet correspond to the RUI locations listed in the YAML file, showing the mapping between the RUI location and the specific millitome and tissue block identifiers.

Figure 8. An example of the registrations.yaml file (left) side-by-side with the lookup table (right), showing how the registered data is linked to the blocks of the millitome.

- The RUI Coordinator generates the rui_locations.jsonld file using the registrations.yaml file and the [RUI Locations Processor](#) developed by the Indiana University team (see **Table 7** for specifications).
- Finally, the rui_locations.jsonld is moved over to the staging location at: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-registrations/tree/main/staging>.

This completes the procedure and makes the mapped millitome (with all the registered data) available in the EUI and other HRA Applications.

Table 7. Data read and generated for linking registered data with mapped millitome blocks using lookup tables.

Input	Output	Tool
<Data Provider>_ <Millitome>_Lookup.xlsx	rui_locations.jsonld at https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-registrations	Python scripts and other custom tooling RUI Locations Processor

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	Published Dataset Graph viewable in the EUI and usable in other HRA applications	(HuBMAP Consortium 2025)
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Glossary

AutoMated Alignment and Projection (AMAP): This acronym refers to the process of aligning two mesh-based 3D models and projecting the underlying data between human atlas systems for data and code interoperability. In the Human Reference Atlas this is used to project registered tissue blocks from a specific source organ to a reference organ.

Blender: Blender is an open-source 3D computer graphics suite of software tools. It supports the full 3D creation pipeline.

digital content creation software: Software used to create and edit digital media, including images, video, audio, 3D models, animations, and more. Blender is one example used frequently in the Human Reference Atlas.

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Exploration User Interface (EUI): An interface developed by MC-IU to explore tissue, see <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>.

lookup table: A tabular mapping of one entity to another, e.g., a phone book (name to number). The millitome lookup table links identification numbers in one system (e.g., Millitome IDs) to corresponding identification numbers in another system (HuBMAP IDs).

millitome: Millitomes provide guidance on how to partition an organ, often a complete organ. Millitomes can include either a 3-dimensional mold that physically holds an organ for partitioning, or a drawing of an organ that is used as a guide by a surgeon when they partition an organ free hand, or both. Using a millitome ensures that tissue sample locations show correctly in the Exploration User Interface.

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